

PID4NFDI Training Concept

Torsten Kahlert and Stephanie Hagemann-Wilholt

17 December 2024

Imprint

Authored by	Torsten Kahlert (https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3264-5006) Stephanie Hagemann-Wilholt (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0474-2410)
Contributions by	Antje Manske (https://orcid.org/0009-0001-0248-4462) Jana Tatscheck (https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1285-2027)
Reviewed by	Nelli Taller (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7992-5668)
Date of publication	17 December 2024
Version	Version 1.0
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267399
License	This work is licensed under https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Deliverable	D3.2 PID4NFDI Training Concept

About

PID4NFDI (<https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi>) is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through Base4NFDI.

Funded by DFG as part of NFDI. DFG Grant Number: 521466146

Abstract

The PID4NFDI project outlines a modular, multi-level training approach to promote the effective use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) across the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). The approach is structured into three levels – Fundamental, Advanced, and Expert – catering to a wide range of users, including researchers, infrastructure managers, data curators, and developers. Each level progressively builds knowledge, from foundational PID concepts and FAIR data management to advanced integration strategies.

Key features of the program include customizable learning paths tailored to specific academic cultures and research methods, with materials designed for various learning preferences. Formats such as videos, webinars, interactive workshops, and group discussions ensure accessibility and engagement. Evaluation and feedback loops are integrated to ensure continuous improvement of the training materials, which will be made openly available.

Abbreviations

API	application programming interface
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Research Foundation)
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	findability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability (FAIR principles)
ID	identifier
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (German National Research Data Infrastructure)
PID	persistent identifier
RDM	research data management

Contents

Introduction	1
General Objectives	2
Modular Approach	3
Level 1 – Fundamental	3
Level 2 – Advanced	4
Level 3 – Expert	4
Cross-Cutting Themes	6
Method	7
Customizable Learning Paths	7
Evaluation and Feedback	7
Publication of Training Materials	7
Appendix	i
Target Group Personas and User Stories	i

Introduction

This concept was developed by PID4NFDI during the first funding phase (initialisation phase) by Base4NFDI. It describes a roadmap for the planned steps to develop training offers and support services for an NFDI-wide PID service in subsequent funding phases.

To promote the effective use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) within NFDI (National Research Data Infrastructure), a comprehensive, modular, and multilevel training service will be provided. This service is designed to address the specific needs of different user groups, including infrastructure managers, researchers, and institutional administrators. By equipping these users with the necessary skills and knowledge, the program aims to enhance the adoption, awareness, and integration of PIDs across the NFDI services. It will highlight best practices for using PIDs, demonstrating successful implementation examples from various disciplines, use cases, different systems and institutions.

The training will follow a scalable model, offering tailored content based on the user's expertise and role. It will include introductory, advanced and expert modules to ensure that all participants, regardless of their prior experience, can fully benefit from the sessions. The concept is inspired by the EduBricks¹ approach and adapts to diverse learning styles and levels of knowledge, thereby ensuring flexibility and adaptability for diverse users. The key concept here is a structured, multi-tier approach offering a progressive learning path, supported by relevant materials and tools for each stage.

To maximize participation and engagement, the training program will be promoted across various communication channels: Regular updates on new training modules and resources will be posted on the PID4NFDI Website; information about upcoming training sessions and new materials will be disseminated through (NFDI) newsletters; targeted announcements will be shared in relevant chat groups, mailing lists, and discussion forums to reach specific user communities and stakeholders.

Identified Requirements

Determining the requirements for PID4NFDI² has shown that the stakeholders for an NFDI-wide PID service already use various information and training formats – with a focus on webinars and support documentation. However, it is difficult to

¹ The modular EduBricks concept is used by the section EduTrain to organize training content into flexible units called EduBricks, allowing instructors to adapt material to audience needs. This approach enables easy maintenance, expansion, and structured, service-oriented teaching resources that support asynchronous collaboration. For further information see EduTrain: [EduBricks: Ein Konzept für modulares und skalierbares Lehrmaterial](#).

² El-Gebali, S., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Böhm, J., & Kahlert, T. (2024). D1.1 Landscape of PID practices within NFDI services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277479>.

derive preferences for certain formats from this as a requirement, as the use of the formats is always linked to their availability. The influence of availability on usage can also be seen in the distribution of the formats used among the respective PID providers as suppliers of the training materials. However, we see an even distribution of information interests between general topics on the use and integration of PIDs and more advanced topics. Direct support is mainly sought for technical integration issues. For information and training material on advanced topics a clear need is expressed by the NFDI representatives surveyed. This result is consistent with the information we gathered from individual consultations with repository managers. In order to further differentiate and prioritize the requirements, we also developed personas and user stories (see [Appendix](#)) to provide information about potential training and support needs.

General Objectives

1. Understanding PIDs: Providing an understanding of the PID landscape, highlighting the importance and benefits of PIDs as well as their integration with FAIR data principles.
2. Customizing knowledge: Tailoring content to specific user groups and their respective responsibilities.
3. Addressing discipline- and method-specific needs: Developing cross-cutting materials while ensuring that specific requirements such as existing standards and established solutions are met.
4. Actionable skills: Fostering hands-on learning through use cases and best practice examples that demonstrate the operational applications of PIDs.

Modular Approach

Level 1 – Fundamental

Objectives:

- Raise awareness and provide information on the PID landscape.
- Explain the benefits and requirements of PIDs in the context of FAIR data management.
- Provide an overview of different types of PIDs and their use cases.

Target Groups:

- Repository managers at early stages of process (conceptual and development phases)
- Data managers and curators (beginner level)
- Decision makers (to understand the strategic value of PIDs)
- Researchers (introduction to PID usage)

Materials & Tools:

- Video Introduction: Explaining the benefits of PIDs, their role in data management and answering general questions
- Video Snippets: Short videos (60-90 seconds) providing quick start information
- Cookbooks³ with:
- Practical guidance on how to obtain PIDs
- Checklists on how to choose PIDs for a specific use case and on basic requirements for minting PIDs and guaranteeing their persistence⁴
- Best Practices: Curated collection of existing training materials, including videos, slides, manuals, wikis from PID providers, services and NFDI consortia and services

³ See PID4NFDI Cookbook <https://pid4nfdi-training.readthedocs.io/en/latest/#> as support to get started with PIDs and further cookbooks on PID registration, e.g. PIDInst <https://docs.pidinst.org/en/latest/datacite-cookbook/index.html>, FAIR Cookbook <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/findability/identifiers.html#fcb-find-identifiers>.

⁴ <https://pid4nfdi-training.readthedocs.io/en/latest/choose.html>.

Level 2 – Advanced

Objectives:

- Provide targeted training materials where gaps are identified in existing materials.
- Focus on integration of multiple PIDs (e.g. PID Graph concept), API usage etc.
- Demonstrate successful PID implementations and their impact in real-world scenarios.

Target Groups:

- Repository managers at early stage of process (experienced/operative level)
- Data managers/curators (experienced/operative level)
- Developers (beginners level in PID integration)
- Project managers (operative level)

Materials & Tools:

- Webinars: Focused sessions (15-30 minutes) on specific use cases allowing participants to explore PID integrations and their transferable applications across contexts (with reasonable half-life expectations; not too and not only technical aspects). The sessions could be adapted for e-learning modules for asynchronous learning.
- Advanced Documentation: Guides on connecting PIDs and API integrations
- Case Studies: Examples of successful implementations

Level 3 – Expert

Objectives:

- Manage large-scale PID outputs and integrate PIDs across the entire research (data) lifecycle with connected PIDs.
- Collaborate with use case stakeholders to solve complex PID-related challenges (e.g. emerging PIDs, versioning) with joint development of resources and documentation.
- Develop systematic approaches to managing PIDs, e.g. integration with ELNs, DMPs.

Target Groups:

- Advanced repository managers and data curators at expert level
- Developers (operative level)
- Working groups within NFDI with specialized scope (e.g. ELN Working Group)
- Trainers and intermediaries providing RDM and PID support

PID4NFDI Training Concept

Materials & Tools:

- **Workshops:** Interactive, based on the train-the-trainer concept designed for expert audiences, focusing on in-depth PID management.
- **Comprehensive Documentation:** Resources from PID providers, including external sources.
- **Customized One-on-One Support:** Personalized assistance for complex PID integration scenarios.
- **Community Collaboration:** Working groups and platforms for joint development of solutions, peer review of implementations, and documentation sharing.
- **Documentation:** Complete references on solutions.

Cross-Cutting Themes

To ensure continuity and scalability across all levels, the following cross-cutting issues should be addressed:

- **Governance and Responsibility:** Develop and deploy training programs that emphasize the responsible management of PIDs for persistence, focusing on roles and governance structures.
- **Regular Consultation Hours:** Offer monthly PID consultation sessions where users can seek expert advice on specific PID-related issues.
- **Iterative Deployment:** Re-use and customize existing PID Guide⁵ for NFDI with continuous feedback from users for refinement.

Figure 1: Example of core functionalities of PID Guide (<https://www.pidwijzer.nl/en>)

⁵ https://www.pidwijzer.nl/en/pid_results/new

Method

The method enables customizable learning paths tailored to diverse needs and learning styles, with integrated evaluation and feedback loops to ensure continuous improvement and relevance of training materials.

Customizable Learning Paths

The concept allows learners to choose their path according to their community-specific needs: Each module can be adapted to the needs of particular academic cultures or employed research methods, with specialized examples and terminology relevant to their research domains.

Materials are designed to cater to different learning goals, depending on the target group, its size, previous knowledge, time for learning, distribution of material and other crucial factors. This includes formats like videos, infographics, webinars, group discussions, consultation hours, and interactive workshops.

Evaluation and Feedback

To create a sustainable, user-centered, and continuously improved training environment, evaluation and feedback mechanisms will be integrated into the development process of new training materials.

- Evaluation Mechanisms: Tests and feedback forms are used to evaluate newly generated materials to assess how effective the materials are for users.
- Iterative Updates: Constant feedback loops ensure that materials evolve and remain relevant over time to meet technological advances and user needs.

Publication of Training Materials

Since the information needs are strongly dependent on the level of knowledge and the target group of the information seekers, well-structured material is a prerequisite for the effectiveness of the knowledge collection we want to provide. Therefore, we will provide an overview of existing training materials from PID providers and services in a format such as Read the Docs to enable easy access to different PID topics and types.

Furthermore, we will use existing repositories to publish our material, such as TIB AV Portal⁶ for videos, Zenodo, twillo – a portal for open educational resources,⁷ and DALIA (Data Literacy Alliance) search portal.⁸ The PID4NFDI website provides

⁶ <https://av.tib.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.twillo.de/oer/web/>

⁸ <https://search.dalia.education/basic>

structured access to the material, sorted by target groups and use cases. By utilizing these repositories, which assign PIDs to the materials, we ensure that our training materials are (machine-readable), discoverable, and reusable, thereby making them available in accordance with FAIR principles.⁹ Additionally, we propose incorporating interactive PID training elements via LiaScript to enhance active learning. These could include quiz questions, step-by-step exercises, or checklists. While LiaScript offers a dynamic platform for such activities, they can also be integrated into traditional text-based materials if needed.

⁹ For criteria of FAIR training materials see: <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-FAIR-training-handbook/#>.

Appendix

Target Group Personas and User Stories

The personas and user stories are derived from the landscape and requirement analysis conducted by PID4NFDI. The personas each represent the expert-level archetype of ideal users of the basic service, while the user stories also take into account the needs from the other two levels.

Repository Manager: Robin

Function/Role	Repository Manager: Product Owner
Activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Content Management: Overseeing the acquisition, organization, and preservation of digital assets, ensuring they are accessible and well-documented. 2. Metadata Quality: Ensuring metadata is accurate, standardized, and interoperable for discoverability and long-term use. 3. Access and Rights Management: Managing access levels, intellectual property rights, and user permissions to ensure compliance with legal and ethical standards. 4. System Maintenance: Maintaining and updating repository systems, troubleshooting issues, and ensuring system security. 5. User Support: Providing training and assistance to users of the repository, including researchers and librarians, to facilitate effective repository use. 6. Policy Development: Establishing and enforcing policies for submission, curation, preservation, and use of repository materials. 7. Collaboration: Working with stakeholders such as IT staff, researchers, and funders to meet repository goals and develop best practices.
Goals	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preservation and Long-Term Access: Ensuring the digital assets are securely preserved and remain accessible over time, supporting the longevity of research outputs.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Enhancing Discoverability: Improving the findability of digital assets through accurate metadata, compliance with standards, and integration with external discovery platforms. 3. Supporting Open Access and FAIR Principles: Facilitating open access to research outputs and ensuring data complies with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. 4. Compliance with Legal and Ethical Standards: Managing rights, licenses, and access to ensure compliance with intellectual property laws, funder mandates, and institutional policies. 5. Promoting Effective Use: Providing support, training, and documentation to enable users to efficiently deposit, retrieve, and reuse digital resources. 6. Optimizing Workflows and Efficiency: Streamlining repository processes through automation and system improvements to reduce administrative burdens and improve accuracy. 7. Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement: Engaging with internal and external stakeholders to ensure the repository meets the needs of its users, supports institutional goals, and stays current with technological advancements.
<p>Pain Points</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resource Constraints: Limited budgets, staff, and technical infrastructure can hinder the ability to effectively manage and maintain repositories, especially as the volume of data grows. 2. Metadata Quality and Consistency: Ensuring high-quality, standardized metadata across diverse datasets and collections can be challenging, particularly when dealing with inconsistent or incomplete data submissions. 3. Interoperability Issues: Integrating repositories with various external systems, databases, and identifiers (e.g., PIDs) while ensuring compliance with evolving standards can create technical complexity. 4. Long-Term Data Preservation: Ensuring the long-term preservation of digital assets in a rapidly changing technological landscape, including addressing format

	<p>obsolescence and ensuring sustainability, poses significant challenges.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. User Engagement and Compliance: Encouraging researchers to deposit their work, provide high-quality metadata, and comply with repository policies can be difficult, especially when researchers are unfamiliar with or resistant to repository processes. 6. Legal and Ethical Compliance: Navigating legal issues around copyright, data privacy, and intellectual property rights while maintaining open access and ensuring compliance with regulations can be a major concern. 7. Scaling and Sustainability: As repositories grow, managing increasing data volumes and ensuring sustainable practices for future growth and technological changes is a constant challenge.
--	---

User Stories

1 Fundamental Level: Understanding PID Basics

As a repository manager, **I want** to learn about the different types of PIDs and their benefits for FAIR data management, **so that** I can raise awareness and provide information to my team on the importance of implementing PIDs in our repository.

- Objective: Enable repository managers to understand the foundational concepts of PIDs to build awareness and communicate the importance of PIDs within their teams effectively.
- Training Focus: Introduction to key PID providers and types, benefits of PIDs, FAIR principles according to PIDs and communication strategies on how to convey the importance of PIDs to team members.

2 Advanced Level: Implementing PID Integration

As a repository manager, **I want** to use training materials that focus on the integration of multiple PIDs and demonstrate the PID Graph concept, **so that** I can successfully implement and utilize PIDs to enhance the interoperability and connectivity of our research outputs.

- Objective: Empower repository managers with the knowledge and skills to integrate different types of PIDs to improve interoperability and findability of repository contents.

- Training Focus: Comprehensive training on implementing multiple PIDs within repository systems, including an introduction to the PID Graph, hands-on integration exercises, and a discussion of how PID use enhances interoperability, citation tracking, and data connectivity.

3 Expert Level: Managing PID Lifecycle Integration

As a repository manager, **I want** to collaborate with stakeholders to develop systematic approaches for managing PIDs throughout the research lifecycle, **so that** we can address complex PID-related challenges such as emerging PIDs and versioning while ensuring seamless integration with e.g. electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) and data management plans (DMPs).

- Objective: Enable repository managers to develop strategies for managing PIDs across the research (data) lifecycle, facilitating collaboration with stakeholders and addressing advanced challenges such as emerging PIDs, versioning and integration with research data management tools.
- Training Focus: Comprehensive guidance on managing PIDs throughout research stages, collaborating with stakeholders, addressing advanced challenges like version control and PID compatibility, and integrating PIDs with tools like ELNs and DMPs for seamless data management.

Researcher: Alex

Function/Role	Researcher: caring about PID integration in RDM
Activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assigning PIDs to Research Data: Assigning PIDs to datasets; choosing reliable repositories for data storage. 2. Linking Resources: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Linking PIDs between datasets and related publications; b. using PIDs to cite datasets correctly in research papers; c. using PIDs to track different versions of datasets, ensuring that changes or updates are clearly identifiable. 3. Contributor Identification: Using ORCID iDs for all contributors; linking ORCID records to research outputs, datasets, and publications. 4. Attributing Resources to Institutions, Projects, Grants: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Assigning organization identifiers (e.g. ROR IDs);

	<p>b. using project and grant identifiers to link datasets to specific research projects or funding sources.</p> <p>5. Meeting External PID Requirements: Ensuring datasets and research outputs comply with funder and publisher mandates requiring the use of PIDs.</p> <p>6. Monitoring and Tracking the Impact of Research Data: Using PIDs to track citations and reuse of research data, leveraging PIDs for datasets to monitor their impact.</p>
Goals	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensuring Persistent Access to Research Data: Guarantee that research data remains accessible, citable, and trackable over time, even if hosting institutions or repositories change. 2. Facilitating Reproducibility and Transparency: Enhance research transparency and reproducibility by creating unique and persistent links between datasets and research publications or other outputs. 3. Attributing Credit Accurately and Transparently: Ensure proper attribution and recognition for all contributors involved in the research process by using persistent identifiers. 4. Tracking Data Versioning and Updates: Keep track of the different versions of data records and ensure continuous traceability of changes over time. 5. Establishing Institutional and Project-Level Attribution: Accurately attribute research to the correct institution, project, or funder for accountability and proper recognition of organizational contributions. 6. Complying with Funder and Publisher Requirements: Meet external mandates from funders and publishers by integrating PIDs into data management workflows, thus ensuring that datasets and publications meet established standards for traceability and citation. 7. Improving Data Discoverability and Reuse: Make research data more discoverable and reusable by properly linking and citing datasets using PIDs. 8. Monitoring and Tracking of own Research Achievements: Track and measure the impact of research data by

	<p>monitoring how often it is cited, used, or referenced by other researchers over time.</p>
Pain Points	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of Institutional Support or Training: Researchers may not have sufficient training in RDM and PID integration, leading to gaps in implementing best practices for data management and citation; e.g.: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Technical Expertise: Researchers may lack the technical knowledge required to ensure persistent access, particularly when integrating PIDs or working with repository software. b. Metadata Expertise: Many researchers struggle to create comprehensive metadata that effectively links PIDs and makes their datasets discoverable. Poor metadata reduces the visibility and reusability of research data. 2. Time Constraints: RDM and PID-related tasks can be seen as extra work on top of research activities, making it difficult for researchers to devote sufficient time to ensure proper data management. E.g. repository selection and costs: Identifying reliable repositories that support long-term storage, versioning, and PID assignment can be overwhelming. Some repositories may charge fees, adding a financial burden. 3. Inconsistent Standards: Variability in data management practices across institutions, disciplines, and repositories can create confusion and inconsistencies, making it harder for researchers to integrate PIDs effectively; e.g.: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Confusion over Versioning Practices: Proper versioning requires clear procedures and documentation, which may be confusing or inconsistently applied, leading to issues in identifying the correct dataset version for citation or use. b. Navigating Complex Requirements: Complying with the varying PID-related requirements of funders and publishers can be complex and time-consuming, as different stakeholders may have

	different expectations for PIDs, data sharing, and citation practices.
--	--

User Stories

1 Fundamental Level: Understanding DOI Benefits for Data Sharing

As a researcher preparing to share my dataset, **I want to** understand how assigning a PID to my data will ensure that it can be persistently accessed and cited, **so that** I can make my research more transparent and reusable.

- Objective: Enable researchers to understand how assigning PIDs to datasets enhances data accessibility, citation, and reusability for transparent, reusable research.
- Training Focus: Explain PID fundamentals and best practices for PID assignment as well as benefits of long-term access and improved data citation.

2 Advanced Level: Linking PIDs

As a researcher managing multiple datasets and publications, **I want to** integrate DOIs for datasets with ORCID iDs for contributors and link these to my institutional identifier, **so that** I can clearly demonstrate the relationships between data, contributors, and institutions in a unified, discoverable way.

- Objective: Provide researchers with skills to integrate dataset DOIs with ORCID iDs and ROR IDs to show relations between contributors, datasets and institutions.
- Training Focus: Hands-on methods for linking PIDs across different entities to create a discoverable network of research resources.

3 Expert Level: Comprehensive PID Integration Across Research (Data) Lifecycle

As a senior researcher managing multiple projects, **I want to** systematically integrate PIDs across my entire research lifecycle, including data versioning with DOIs, linking them to electronic lab notebooks (ELNs), and incorporating them into my data management plan (DMP), **so that** I can ensure seamless tracking and impact monitoring across my research outputs.

- Objective: Guide senior researchers in implementing PIDs systematically across the research (data) lifecycle for effective data versioning, ELN integration, and impact monitoring.
- Training Focus: Strategies for lifecycle-based PID integration, including data versioning, linking to ELNs, and incorporating PIDs into DMPs for seamless research tracking.

Decision Maker: Monica

Function/Role	Decision Maker: managing a research organization or unit within an organization
Activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strategic Planning for PID Integration: Develop and implement a comprehensive strategy for integrating PIDs (such as DOIs, ORCID iDs, ROR IDs) across the research data lifecycle. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Establish institutional goals for PID use that align with open science and FAIR data management principles. b. Create a roadmap for the gradual integration of PIDs, identifying key milestones for implementation across departments and research projects. c. Engage with key stakeholders (e.g., IT departments, librarians, and research staff) to ensure that PID integration is practical and aligned with institutional needs. 2. Creating and Enforcing PID Policies: Establish institutional policies that mandate the use of PIDs in research outputs, datasets, and publications and ensure compliance of these policies with external requirements from funders and publishers. 3. Investing in PID Infrastructure: Ensure the institution has the necessary technical infrastructure to support the use of PIDs across research workflows and to ensure system interoperability. 4. Allocate Resources for Training and Support: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Create or support educational materials and training programs that highlight how PIDs enhance research integrity, reproducibility, and data discoverability. b. Provide ongoing support through research data management (RDM) offices or data stewards who can assist researchers with PID integration. 5. Facilitating Cross-Departmental Collaboration: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Foster collaboration between research departments, IT, and external partners to ensure

	<p>the seamless integration of PIDs across the institution.</p> <p>b. Work with PID providers to ensure your institution stays aligned with best practices and emerging trends.</p> <p>6. Fostering a Culture of Open Science and Data Stewardship: Lead initiatives that promote a culture of open science and data stewardship across the institution.</p> <p>7. Tracking Research Impact and Reporting with PIDs: Use PIDs to enhance reporting capabilities for the institution’s research activities.</p> <p>8. Advocating for Policy Change at National and International Level: Participate in policy discussions with funders, national research bodies, and international organizations to ensure the broad integration of PIDs into research infrastructure.</p> <p>9. Support Adoption of New Developments in RDM Landscape: Proactively adopt new PIDs for emerging needs (e.g., for research instruments, protocols, or tools) and ensure the institution stays ahead of trends in digital research management.</p>
Goals	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sustained Research Access & Institutional Legacy: Ensure long-term access to research outputs via PIDs to preserve the institution’s intellectual legacy and support enduring contributions to knowledge. 2. Maximizing Research Discoverability and Visibility: Enhance the global reach and impact of the institution’s research by embedding PIDs across outputs, ensuring streamlined discoverability. 3. Commitment to Open Science and FAIR Compliance: Position the institution as an advocate of open science by incorporating PIDs into workflows to fulfill FAIR principles and promote transparency and accessibility. 4. Safeguarding Research Integrity and Attribution: Strengthen institutional integrity by ensuring accurate, traceable research attribution through standardized PID practices.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Ensuring Compliance & Funding Alignment: Meet funder, publisher, and regulatory mandates on PID use, ensuring the institution remains competitive and compliant in the research landscape. 6. Enhancing Research Efficiency & Data Management: Simplify data management and lifecycle tracking through PIDs, reducing administrative burdens and supporting research reusability. 7. Tracking Research Impact & Institutional Influence: Leverage PIDs to monitor research impact, data reuse, and citation metrics, illustrating the institution’s contributions and influence. 8. Promoting Data Stewardship & Best Practices: Foster a culture of data stewardship by training researchers in PID best practices, enhancing the institution’s commitment to exemplary data management.
<p>Pain Points</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Awareness and Education: Difficulty in educating stakeholders about the value and importance of PIDs. 2. Cultural Resistance: Resistance to changing established workflows and practices. Difficulty in showing immediate impact to convince researchers of PID value. 3. System Fragmentation: Disparate and fragmented systems that make PID integration difficult. 4. Technical and Infrastructure Challenges: Lack of infrastructure to support PID management and integration. 5. Cost and Resource Limitations: Financial and human resource constraints affecting implementation and managing PID as well as efforts for providing knowledge on PID management in the organization and for the users 6. Ensuring Compliance: Difficulty in enforcing consistent use of PIDs across all research outputs. 7. Complexity of Linking PIDs: Challenges in managing and linking multiple PIDs from different providers. 8. Navigating External Requirements: Complexities in meeting funder, publisher, and international PID mandates. 9. Impact Measurement: Challenges in setting up systems to track and measure research impact using PIDs.

	<p>10. Long-Term Stewardship: Ensuring the sustainability of PID-based data stewardship over the long term.</p> <p>11. Evolving Standards: Managing the integration of emerging PID types and staying updated with evolving standards.</p> <p>12. Stakeholder Coordination: Difficulty in coordinating across diverse internal and external stakeholders.</p>
--	--

User Stories

1 Fundamental Level: Understanding PIDs for Promoting FAIR Data Management

As a research manager, **I want to** understand the different types of PIDs and their roles in managing research data, **so that** I can promote awareness of FAIR principles among my team.

- Objective: To build foundational knowledge of different types of PIDs and their role in research data management.
- Training Focus: Introducing key concepts of PIDs and their function in promoting FAIR principles, along with best practice examples.

2 Advanced Level: Training on PID Integration and API Usage

As a research manager, **I want to** access targeted training materials on integrating multiple PIDs and utilizing APIs effectively, **so that** I can ensure our research projects leverage PIDs to improve data interoperability and collaboration among teams.

- Objective: Develop knowledge about integrating multiple PIDs and utilizing APIs for enhanced PID management.
- Training Focus: Hands-on training on connecting PIDs.

3 Expert Level: Establishing PID Integration for Organizational Reporting

As a director of my organization, **I want to** establish a systematic approach for integrating PIDs into our reporting processes, **so that** we can meet external stakeholders' requirements for transparency and accountability in our research outputs.

- Objective: Implement a structured approach for using PIDs in reporting systems (CRIS), meeting transparency and accountability standards.
- Training Focus: Strategic training on integrating PIDs into reporting systems (CRIS), aligning with institutional policies, and stakeholder requirements for impact tracking and accountability.

Trainer: Andrea

Function/Role	Trainer/Intermediary (e.g. data stewards, research data managers): offering FDM trainings including PIDs as topic
Activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Awareness and Education <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Raise Awareness: Explain the importance of PIDs and their role in improving research data management (FAIR principles). b. Provide Basic Training: Introduce fundamental concepts like different types of PIDs (DOIs, ORCID iDs, etc.) and their use cases. c. Promote Best Practices: Share guidelines for effectively using PIDs to increase data findability, accessibility, and citation. 2. Curriculum Development <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Design Training Materials: Create targeted and structured training content (e.g., presentations, guides, exercises) based on the audience's needs and experience levels (fundamental to expert). b. Update Materials: Regularly revise training materials to reflect new developments in PID technologies and evolving standards. 3. Tailored Training Sessions <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Provide Custom Solutions: Adapt training programs to the specific needs of repository managers or researchers, addressing discipline-specific PID use cases. b. Hands-on Learning: Organize workshops and interactive sessions to help users integrate PIDs into their workflows and systems (e.g., API usage, PID Graph). c. Practical Use Cases: Demonstrate real-world applications of PIDs in research projects, repositories, and metadata management. 4. Support and Consultation <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Offer Ongoing Support: Act as a point of contact for repository managers and researchers after training, providing help with the implementation of PID systems and addressing issues.

	<p>b. Consultation on PID Integration: Guide institutions on how to incorporate PIDs into their infrastructure, such as repositories, DMPs, or ELNs.</p> <p>5. Monitoring and Feedback</p> <p>a. Gather Feedback: Collect input from trainees to evaluate training effectiveness and identify areas for improvement.</p> <p>b. Monitor Adoption: Track how well repository managers and researchers implement PIDs in their daily workflows post-training.</p> <p>6. Collaboration with Stakeholders</p> <p>a. Engage with PID Providers: Maintain communication with external PID providers to ensure accurate information is shared in training and keep up-to-date with their latest tools and services.</p> <p>b. Work Across Teams: Collaborate with institutional stakeholders, technical staff, and project leads to ensure training aligns with organizational goals and policies.</p>
<p>Goals</p>	<p>1. Enhance PID Adoption and Improve RDM Practices: Increase awareness among repository managers and researchers about the importance of PIDs for advancing FAIR principles, and encourage consistent PID use across systems. Promote best practices in data management by leveraging PIDs for reliable identification, linking, and tracking of research outputs, thereby enhancing data discoverability and accessibility within repositories and research workflows.</p> <p>2. Deliver Targeted Training for Independent PID Implementation and Management: Provide hands-on training to equip repository managers and researchers with the practical skills to integrate PIDs into daily workflows, covering both technical processes (e.g., API usage, PID Graph) and strategy development, enabling them to independently implement and maintain PID systems.</p> <p>3. Support the Development of PID Infrastructure and Technical Interoperability: Facilitate the adoption and</p>

	<p>integration of PID systems within institutions by building seamless connections with external PID providers, ensuring that repositories and data management platforms can handle PIDs consistently to enhance metadata quality and compatibility.</p> <p>4. Reduce Barriers to PID Usage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Simplify PID Integration: Address common challenges and reduce technical or procedural barriers that prevent repository managers and researchers from adopting PIDs. b. Minimize Administrative Burden: Help users automate workflows and reduce manual metadata entries through efficient PID implementation, saving time and effort. <p>5. Ensure Long-Term Sustainability of PID Systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Support Future-Proofing: Help repository managers and researchers design systems that ensure long-term sustainability and scalability of PID usage across the research lifecycle. b. Encourage Best Practices for Data Citation: Promote proper citation practices by using PIDs, helping researchers maintain credit for their work and ensuring persistence over time.
<p>Pain Points</p>	<p>1. Low Awareness and Engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Lack of Understanding: Many researchers are unfamiliar with PIDs or do not see the immediate value, making it difficult to get buy-in for training and adoption. b. Resistance to Change: Established workflows without PIDs may be deeply entrenched, leading to resistance when introducing new processes or technologies. <p>2. Technical Complexity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c. Technical Integration Issues: Explaining the technical aspects of PIDs (e.g., API integration, metadata management, PID Graph) to non-technical audiences can be challenging, especially if the infrastructure at their institutions is outdated or fragmented.

	<p>d. Inconsistent Systems: Differences in the technology used across various repositories, systems, and institutions make it hard to provide standardized training and support.</p> <p>3. Gaps in Existing Resources</p> <p>e. Lack of Tailored Training Materials: Available resources might not address the specific needs of different audiences (e.g. advanced users vs. beginners), requiring trainers to develop custom materials, which can be time-consuming.</p> <p>f. Evolving PID Landscape: The rapid development of PID-related technologies and standards requires continuous updates to training materials, making it hard to stay current.</p> <p>4. Institutional and Organizational Barriers</p> <p>g. Lack of Institutional Support: Institutions may lack policies, funding, or technical infrastructure to fully implement PIDs, making it difficult for trainers to ensure long-term impact.</p> <p>h. Silos within Organizations: Lack of coordination between departments (IT, research management, library) may hinder the adoption of PIDs, despite efforts to provide training.</p> <p>5. Measuring Impact and Adoption</p> <p>i. Difficulty in Tracking Progress: It is often challenging to assess the long-term impact of training programs, including how effectively participants implement PID systems in their daily work.</p> <p>j. Sustained Engagement: Ensuring that participants continue to engage with and apply the skills they learned in training can be difficult, especially when faced with competing priorities.</p> <p>6. Administrative Overhead</p> <p>k. Limited Time and Resources: Trainers may face limited time and resources to create effective, ongoing training programs, especially when tasked with supporting a large number of repositories or researchers.</p> <p>l. Follow-up Support: Providing adequate post-training support and troubleshooting for PID</p>
--	--

	integration is resource-intensive and not always possible with existing bandwidth.
--	--

User Stories

1 Fundamental Level: Introduction to PIDs

As a training facilitator, **I want to** provide repository managers and researchers with a basic understanding of what PIDs are and why they are important, **so that** they can identify the right types of PIDs to use in their research workflows and improve FAIR data management practices.

- Objective: Raise awareness about the role of PIDs in ensuring data findability and accessibility.
- Training Focus: Introduce the different types of PIDs and their use cases in research data management.

2 Advanced Level: Integration of Multiple PIDs

As a trainer, **I want to** teach repository managers how to integrate multiple PIDs (e.g., for datasets, contributors, organizations) into their repository systems and demonstrate how the PID Graph concept can be used to map and connect resources, **so that** they can streamline data linking and citation processes.

- Objective: Provide hands-on guidance for integrating PIDs across systems.
- Training Focus: Usage of API to manage PIDs, practical examples of connecting research outputs using the PID Graph.

3 Expert Level: Managing Complex PID Infrastructures

As an expert training facilitator, **I want to** guide repository managers on how to manage complex PID ecosystems across the entire research lifecycle, including PID versioning and handling emerging PID standards, **so that** they can support large-scale research projects and ensure metadata accuracy over time.

- Objective: Enable repository managers to handle advanced PID challenges like versioning and integration with ELNs and DMPs.
- Training Focus: Developing systematic approaches to PID management, collaborative problem-solving for advanced PID issues.